

Unique and creative story-telling.

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Wild Wise Weird*”

Robert Cort, Melissye

United States, January 10th and 11th, 2025.* * *

Robert Cort: Very thoughtful

This book shares fun stories about a bird village and its leader, Kingfisher, while showing Vietnamese culture. Full of adventure and life lessons, it's perfect for fans of fantasy and unique tales. [1]

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Screenshot. Review of “*Wild Wise Weird*” by Robert Cort [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 10th, 2025.

Melissye: Loved the creative stories!

This book was a pleasant surprise – different from what I expected, but in a good way. Through the experiences of Kingfisher and his village, it explores life, the environment, and navigating questions we don't always have answers to. It also touches on feeling inadequate and how Kingfisher handled it at times. I think that, in some way, we can all relate :). The stories were creative and fun, with a few cliffhangers that left me curious to read more. [2].

melissye

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Verified Purchase

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Screenshot. Review of “*Wild Wise Weird*” by Melissye [2]. Reviewed in the United States on January 11th, 2025.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Robert Cort, Melissye's reviews [1, 2] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [3]. The reprint's title is created based on the review's content.

References

[1] Robert Cort (2025, Jan. 10). Very thoughtful. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R17MA2RLUPH5D5>

[2] Melissye (2025, Jan. 11). Loved the creative stories!
<https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2Y0TP4FSM6B5P>

[3] Vuong, Q. H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6/>